

DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES AND HIGH-QUALITY STANDARDS IN S.C. JUNGHEINRICH ROMANIA S.R.L.

Author(s)*: Zsolt TOTH ¹, Ionela-Roxana PUIU ², Shih-Shuan WANG ³, Eugen-Silviu VRĂJITORU ⁴,
Mircea BOȘCOIANU ⁵

Position: PhD Student¹, PhD Student², PhD Student³, PhD Student⁴, Prof., PhD⁵

University: Transilvania University of Brasov

Address: Brasov, B-dul Eroilor, No. 29, Romania

Email: zsolt.toth@unitbv.ro ¹, ionela.puiu@unitbv.ro ², shih-shuan.wang@unitbv.ro ³,
eugen.vrajitoru@unitbv.ro ⁴, boscoianu.mircea@yahoo.com ⁵

Webpage: <https://www.unitbv.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – highlighting the dynamic capabilities and high-quality standards in a multinational company that in the pandemic year 2021 recorded the best year in its history, reaching a turnover of over four billion euros.

Methodology/approach – holding a brainstorming session for creating ten working options, analyzing them according to ten relevant criteria in an advanced multi-criteria analysis and establishing their final ranking using a mathematical formula.

Findings – Jungheinrich is a green company which demonstrates high competence in consultative sales and after-sales service, fast response time, quality service to 5-star group-wide standards and customized solutions.

Research limitations/implications – the research is limited to the brainstorming ideas outlined and the results obtained from the advanced multi-criteria analysis of the resulting work options, with implications for future improvement of internal procedures.

Practical implications – there are strong foreign companies in Romania, which continuously reinvest their profits and can use the local market to optimize the development of the whole group.

Originality/value – conducting a quantitative and qualitative research on a German multinational company, which is developing in Romania using managerial know-how with almost 70 years of experience and which is in the top 50 best employers in Germany.

Key words: Jungheinrich, electric, logistics.

Introduction

In an ever-changing world, the dynamic capabilities of individuals and organisations become extremely important. These represent the ability to adapt to new situations, to face new challenges, to be always competitive and to have the power to develop continuously and sustainably (e.g., Helfat et al., 2007; Boșcoianu, Prelipcean and Lupan, 2018). Universally accepted quality standards exist worldwide, without which organisations cannot develop and contribute to technological development and overall economic growth. (e.g., Ronnen, 1991; Blind and Hipp, 2003).

At Jungheinrich there are certificates such as Eco Vadis for sustainability activities on a CSR performance monitoring platform, ISO 9001 ensuring the most significant standard in quality management at the production sites, ISO 14001 for the foundation in terms of active and effective environmental and sustainability performance, ISO 14040 certifying the first product life cycle assessment for a manufacturer of industrial trucks, ISO 50001 for energy management systems and ISO/IEC 27001 certifying the information security management system.

The brainstorming architecture and options selection

Our brainstorming session resulted in 90 innovative ideas from the ten most experienced employees of the Jungheinrich Business Services Center in Brasov, which were grouped into ten categories of eight,

nine or ten ideas each. The grouped ideas were used to construct paragraphs called work options (e.g., Wilson, 2013).

Option A: Good working conditions, pleasant atmosphere and helpful colleagues increase the cohesion of the employees. Offering complete modern equipment for hybrid home/office work increases employee enthusiasm for work.

Option B: Jungheinrich offers ongoing, sustained and effective online training for employees. To develop team spirit and encourage sports, physical and virtual meetings, thematic team buildings and frequent trips with colleagues are organised.

Option C: The opening of a Business Services Center in Brasov is part of Jungheinrich's development strategy. The gap between countries is reduced through an organised flow of information and the use of modern communication channels. It is intended to use local suppliers and to conclude contracts with them for large values.

Option D: According to the principles of team leadership, to avoid employee overload, the team will be expanded into new spaces with a slow adaptation of new colleagues. Coordination between departments and the dense organisational chart should be optimised, as inherent imbalances such as the uncertainty of war constantly arise.

Option E: Implementing future technologies requires investment in research, development and innovation of competitive products. Market dynamics and the need for continuous improvement force the company to use up-to-date software and to optimize the website.

Option F: Jungheinrich is a green company with its own electric charging stations and has stopped the production of diesel-powered forklift trucks. It wants to develop new electric equipment with lithium-ion batteries, which have a low carbon footprint. Although lithium-ion batteries cost twice as much as lead-acid batteries, modern lithium-ion technology is more cost-effective.

Option G: Jungheinrich offers its customers comprehensive services and solutions for the equipment it sells. Support in the use of the equipment is offered and quality standards are imposed on customers. To be close to the current needs of the companies, used equipment is offered for rent, the share of online trade is increasing and back-office support team for sales representatives is being developed.

Option H: Multinational organizational culture and German management ensure optimized complexity and compliance with legal requirements. The gradual implementation of the automation of procedures is carried out in consultation with colleagues and in accordance with planned schedules. To improve Jungheinrich's image, donations are made to charities and the customer evaluation service is outsourced.

Option I: To ensure speedy deliveries, transport services have been outsourced. Logistics optimisation is achieved through customised hubs and the development of own vertical warehouses. Jungheinrich is ready to get involved in PNRR projects with sales-related stocks and its own showroom.

Option J: Jungheinrich offers competitive advantages through competitive products and all-inclusive maintenance contracts. The after sales department maintains new and used equipment with original spare parts and specialised service technicians.

An application for the advanced multi-criteria analysis of the resulting work options

The ten analysis criteria were established by the authors based on their scientific experience and considering current market conditions and constraints:

Criterion 1: dynamic capabilities paradigm

Criterion 2: logistics management

Criterion 3: procurement digitalisation

Criterion 4: National Recovery and Resilience Plan

Criterion 5: European Green Deal

Criterion 6: electrical logistics equipment production

Criterion 7: electrical logistics equipment refurbishment

Criterion 8: high-quality standards

Criterion 9: management challenges and opportunities

Criterion 10: post-pandemic reality

The criteria are compared two by two, giving a value of two for the most important criterion, a value of one in case of a tie or when the same two criteria are compared and a value of zero for the least important criterion. (Table 1) A total, a hierarchy by level and a weight for each criterion are calculated by a mathematical formula. (Figure 1) For the analysis of the ten work options according to the ten established criteria, single non-repeatable scores from one to ten are awarded (Table 2). To establish a final ranking of the options, the weights for each criterion are multiplied by the scores awarded and the results obtained are added together for each option (e.g., Toth et al., 2022b). The highest ranked option in the analysis is option F (Table 3). According to this option, Jungheinrich is a modern company that is abandoning outdated technologies and investing in new and innovative technologies.

Table 1. Calculating the weight of each criterion

Criterion	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀	Total	Level	Weight
C ₁	1	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	11	4,5	1,88
C ₂	0	1	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	9	6	1,30
C ₃	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	8,5	0,45
C ₄	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	10	0,17
C ₅	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	2	7	7	0,85
C ₆	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	0	0	0	13	3	2,77
C ₇	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	11	4,5	1,88
C ₈	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	19	1	8,90
C ₉	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	2	17	2	5,64
C ₁₀	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	1	5	8,5	0,45

$$W = \frac{CT + (CT - LT) + CP + 0,5}{(HT - CT) + \frac{NC}{2}}$$

- W – weight
- CT – each criterion total
- LT – lowest criterion total
- CP – number of criteria passed
- HT – highest criterion total
- NC – total number of criteria

Figure 1. Weight calculation

Table 2. Scores awarded to each work option according to each criterion

Criterion	Options	O _A	O _B	O _C	O _D	O _E	O _F	O _G	O _H	O _I	O _J
C ₁		8	9	10	9	8	6	8	8	6	5
C ₂		6	7	6	6	6	3	6	3	8	6
C ₃		5	5	5	5	4	4	3	2	5	4
C ₄		1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	4	1
C ₅		2	2	1	1	2	5	2	7	1	2
C ₆		3	3	3	3	7	8	5	5	2	7

C ₇	4	4	4	4	3	7	4	6	3	8
C ₈	10	10	8	8	10	10	10	10	10	10
C ₉	9	8	9	10	9	9	9	9	9	9
C ₁₀	7	6	7	7	5	2	7	4	7	3

Table 3. Calculation of the final hierarchy of options

Options \ Criterion	O _A	O _B	O _C	O _D	O _E	O _F	O _G	O _H	O _I	O _J
C ₁	15,0	16,9	18,8	16,9	15,0	11,3	15,0	15,0	11,3	9,4
C ₂	7,8	9,1	7,8	7,8	7,8	3,9	7,8	3,9	10,4	7,8
C ₃	2,3	2,3	2,3	2,3	1,8	1,8	1,4	0,9	2,3	1,8
C ₄	0,2	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,7	0,2
C ₅	1,7	1,7	0,9	0,9	1,7	4,3	1,7	6,0	0,9	1,7
C ₆	8,3	8,3	8,3	8,3	19,4	22,2	13,9	13,9	5,5	19,4
C ₇	7,5	7,5	7,5	7,5	5,6	13,2	7,5	11,3	5,6	15,0
C ₈	89,0	89,0	71,2	71,2	89,0	89,0	89,0	89,0	89,0	89,0
C ₉	50,8	45,1	50,8	56,4	50,8	50,8	50,8	50,8	50,8	50,8
C ₁₀	3,2	2,7	3,2	3,2	2,3	0,9	3,2	1,8	3,2	1,4
Total	185,7	182,8	171,0	174,7	193,6	197,4	190,3	192,7	179,6	196,4
Final hierarchy of options	6	7	10	9	3	1	5	4	8	2

Discussion and conclusions

Jungheinrich was the first manufacturer to implement lithium-ion batteries in materials handling equipment more than ten years ago. Jungheinrich presented the first lithium-ion battery equipment model at the CeMAT 2008 trade fair. At CeMAT 2011, Jungheinrich was the first company in the world to present the series production launch of a lithium-ion battery-powered pallet truck, which featured higher safety, no maintenance and a longer life cycle. The battery weighed only 14 kg and reduced the weight of the equipment by 150 kg compared to lead-acid batteries equipment. Changing the battery was simple, with a suitcase-like handle. LogiMAT 2018 saw the unveiling of the first forklift truck with lithium-ion battery, revolutionising logistics equipment production.

Lithium-ion batteries are two-thirds smaller than lead-acid batteries, which has helped create compact equipment sizes, more space for forklift operators, greater safety and stability and are more cost-effective and sustainable. Jungheinrich contributed to the development of these batteries from the very beginning, when the price of lithium-ion cells was ten times higher than today. Since 2014 the trend has changed due to lower costs and longer periods of use, now batteries no longer need to be changed regularly, some being incorporated. Lithium-ion batteries cost twice as much as lead-acid batteries, but over time they prove to be more efficient. Although they consume more energy during production, they have a 21 percent smaller carbon footprint than lead-acid batteries. Lithium-ion technology is expected to be the standard within five years and refurbishing used batteries will extend the life of the cells.

A new model of lithium-ion technology-based equipment, with a new design and compact dimensions for narrow aisles, was considered "Best of the Best" by the Red Dot Design Award jury in 2021. It recognises that it is in a truck using an ultrasonic sensor that automatically activates the headlights to illuminate the loading area and reduces speed giving more safety. By replacing 48-volt technology with 24-volt technology, energy savings of up to 30 percent are achieved. The company has joined the Science Based Targets group, using only green energy in Germany and will implement this principle in other countries. To generate its own solar energy, some sites are equipped with photovoltaic systems.

EcoVadis rating agency has awarded Jungheinrich its highest sustainability certificate of platinum in 2021, which ranks the company among the most sustainable one percent of the world's companies out of more than 85,000 companies rated. Jungheinrich combines social and environmental responsibility with profitable growth, shaping the intralogistics services and logistics platforms of the future. Highlights

include environmental measures, its own labour and human rights code, sustainable procurement, commitment to the Paris climate goal of a 1.5-degree temperature reduction and the desire to achieve group-wide climate neutrality.

Former Formula 1 world champion Nico Rosberg became Jungheinrich's brand ambassador in 2021 until 2025 and will represent the company in promoting the campaign "we are the pioneers of intralogistics" in the process of digitalization, globalization, opening up to Asia, urbanization, density, climate change, resource scarcity, e-commerce, innovation, sustainability, electric mobility, integrated solutions, electric drive, automation, promoting the green economy and vertical agriculture in Kuwait in small spaces.

The company is highly competitive in its products and services, invests heavily in research, has a multinational organizational culture, has weathered the supply chain disruption during the coronavirus crisis by quickly finding alternative sources of supply and participates in corporate social responsibility programs. Since 2012 Jungheinrich donates annually to humanitarian actions in Tanzania, Haiti, Afghanistan and DR Congo. Jungheinrich actively participates in increasing the logistics flow and automated logistics capabilities of its customers through warehouse redevelopment, modern transport systems, fleet management system to improve productivity and increase warehouse security. To expand into the market of automated warehouse logistics systems, the automation company Arculus was acquired in 2021, which produces autonomous mobile robots and software solutions for mobile automation.

As a result of managerial implications, the company is growing faster than anticipated in all six areas of activity: automation, digitalisation, energy systems, efficiency, global footprint and sustainability. Besides intralogistics, it plans to expand into electric construction machines, agricultural machines and complete energy solution in collaboration with other companies. Hybrid working and creating a digital working environment at the highest level will attract quality human resources. From 2021 Jungheinrich has been relisted in the MDAX index, from 2022 the company implements a gender-neutral language and from 2023 a new plant will open in the Czech Republic, which will produce reach trucks. By 2025, the aim is to achieve revenues of 5.5-billion-euro, 20 percent revenue outside Europe, 70 percent lithium-ion equipment and continuous improvement, over 18 percent of managers to be women and climate neutrality as a sustainability factor.

The main contributions of this research are related to brainstorming ideas of the ten most experienced employees from the Jungheinrich Business Services Center in Brasov. The advantages of this research are expressed through the development of a multinational company, world leader in intralogistics solutions, which in the pandemic year 2021 had its best year ever with a turnover of over four billion euros and the potential for future growth in the coming post-pandemic years, respecting the European Green Deal provisions and the investment opportunities offered by the Next Generation EU funding.

The limitations of this research are related to the brainstorming ideas, the analysis criteria, the advanced multi-criteria analysis of the work options resulting from brainstorming session, the mathematical formula used, the final options ranking and the information collected from internal company sources. Future research will consist of analysing the company's progress in achieving the 2025 strategy goals, investing in new technologies, reducing costs and resource consumption. A new refurbishment plant will be developed in 2022 in Ploiesti, Romania, where some old components of used electric forklift trucks and electric pallet trucks will be replaced with new ones and other components will be cleaned and repainted, the resulting product being very similar to a new one.

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